

Some Benzyl Arylamidino-aryldithiocarbamates and their Oxidative Debenzylation and Cyclisation into 3-Arylimino-4-aryl-5-thio-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines

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A few arylamidino chlorides have been condensed with benzyl aryldithiocarbamates, affording the related benzyl arylamidino-aryldithiocarbamates (hydrochlorides) which on oxidative debenzoylation and cyclisation have been shown to form the related 3-arylimino-4-aryl-5-thio-1, 2, 4-thiadiazolidines.

Since amidino-thio systems containing the grouping $R.NH(X:)C:NH-C(:S)-$ are easily oxidised, where X is $=NH$ or $=S$, into 5-membered heterocycles, e.g. 1, 2, 4-thiadiazolidines¹ or 1, 2, 4-dithiazolidines², a probable approach to the synthesis of 3-arylimino-4-aryl-5-thio-1, 2, 4-thiadiazolidines (I) could be through the oxidation of the related arylamidino-aryldithiocarbamic acids (II). Thus:

The arylamidinoaryldithiocarbamic acids (II) or their salts could not, however, be prepared directly by the usual reaction of carbon disulphide with the required amines, in this case the NN' -diarylguanidines. Their S -benzyl derivatives (IV) were therefore prepared by an extension of Pandeya⁴ and Joshua's³ synthesis and oxidatively debenzoylated and cyclised into the 3-arylimino-4-aryl-5-thio-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines (I) by Verma's technique⁵.

By analogy with the reaction of cyanamides and thiocarbamides^{3,4}, an arylocyanamide on reaction with benzyl aryldithiocarbamate was expected to afford one or more of the following products (III through VI):

1. Dixit, this *Journal*, 1961, **38**, 221; 1960, **37**, 151.
2. *Idem, ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 46.
3. Joshua, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, **21B**, 588.
4. Pandeya, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 525.
5. Verma, Ph.D. Thesis, Banaras Hindu University, 1963.

The sulphides of type (III) are known only in the form of their salts which are quite unstable⁴. On basification and warming, these readily rearrange^{7,8} into isomeric amidinothiocarbamide type derivatives or decompose to the related thiocarbamides, cyanamides, and guanidines. These also do not undergo orderly oxidation. Since the product, now isolated, is quite stable as a salt or as a free base and does not rearrange into another product but undergoes easy oxidation to 3-arylimino-4-aryl-5-thio-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (I), structure (IV) is assigned to it.

Verma^{5,6} using bromine/iodine in solvents like chloroform and carbon tetrachloride achieved oxidative debenylation, followed by cyclisation, of a number of 2-*S*-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets including the isothiobiurets (V) and (VI), converting them to the related 1,2,4-dithiazolidines⁵⁻⁶. He was, however, not successful in debenzylating and cyclising *S*-benzylisocamidinothiocarbamides into the related 1,2,4-thiadiazolidines. The oxidative debenylation and cyclisation of *S*-benzyl *N*-arylamidino-aryldithiocarbamate hydrochloride (IV) into the related thiadiazolidine (I) was therefore of particular interest. As suggested by Verma⁵, the reaction was probably initiated at the sulphur atom and a sulphenyl bromide intermediate preceded the cyclic product. These changes could be depicted as follows:

For the oxidation product of (IV), three structures, viz., 3-arylimino-4-aryl-5-thio-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (I), 2-aryl-3-imino-4-aryl-5-thio-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (VIII), and 2-thio-3-arylamidinobenzothiazole (IX) are probable.

7. Pandeya, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 1, 275.

8. Suresh, *this Journal*, 1960, 37, 483.

The product was found unreactive towards phenyl isocyanate, phenyl isothiocyanate, carbon disulphide, and nitrous acid. Prolonged boiling with moderately strong acids and alkalis did not effect any changes. It could not also be benzoylated. The group $>C=NH$ as in (VIII) or (IX) is thus probably not present in its structure. There is also some evidence indicating that when alternative possibilities of ring-closure exist, a 1,2,4-thiadiazolidine with a Δ -Ar group in position 2 (as in VIII) is not formed⁹⁻¹¹.

On prolonged treatment with warm ethanolic alkaline sulphide, diphenylguanidine was found to result in considerable quantities. This could arise only from (I) or (VIII), a benzothiazole nucleus as in (IX) being too stable for such decomposition. On these grounds, structure (I) is assigned to the oxidation product of (IV).

The IR absorption characteristics of (I) showed many points of similarity with the IR spectrum of Hector's bases¹¹ which have been shown to be 3-arylimino-4-aryl-5-imino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines. These will be discussed elsewhere.

EXPERIMENTAL

The required benzyl arylthiocarbamates¹²⁻¹⁵ and arylamidine chlorides^{16,17} were obtained by the usual methods, former by benzylation of the arylammonium dithiocarbamates^{12,13} with benzyl chloride and latter, by the action of hydrogen chloride on dry ethereal solutions of the appropriate arylethanamides obtained by dehydro-sulphurisation of the related 1-arylthiocarbamides^{16,17}.

Expt. 1. Interaction of Benzyl Phenylthiocarbamate and Phenylamidine Chloride: Formation of Benzyl Phenylamidinophenylthiocarbamate Hydrochloride (IVa) and Bis-phenylformamidine Sulphide Dihydrochloride (VIIa)

Details of a typical experiment are as follows: Acetone solutions of benzyl phenylthiocarbamate¹³ (6 g. in 40 ml) and phenylamidine chloride¹⁶ (5 g. in 50 ml) were mixed and cooled to -5° in a freezing mixture. Within a few minutes a colorless fluffy product started separating and on keeping for about 1 hr., a light, colorless, water soluble solid (3 g.), m.p. 156° , identified as bis-phenylamidine sulphide dihydrochloride, was filtered (*vide infra*). The filtrate on further keeping for a few hours deposited (4 g.) a water-insoluble product, m.p. 157° , shown to be *S*-benzyl *N*-phenylamidinophenylthiocarbamate hydrochloride (IVa). The remaining mother liquor on evaporation provided a low melting solid, m.p. 73° , identified as dibenzyl disulphide by its underpressed mixed m.p. with an authentic sample.

When the reaction between arylamidine chloride and benzyl arylthiocarbamate was carried out with intense cooling of the acetone medium ($\approx -15^\circ$), the compound (IVa)

9. Joshua and Verma, this *Journal*, 1961, **38**, 988.

10. Kurzer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2345.

11. Joshua, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 392.

12. Losanitsch, *Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 3022.

13. Heller and Bauer, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1902, [2], **65**, 371.

14. Losanitsch, *Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 3026.

15. Braun, *Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 3384.

16. Sahasrabudhey and Krall, this *Journal*, 1941, **18**, 225.

17. Singh *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1946, **23**, 373.

was found to be the sole product of the reaction with yields higher. Effective cooling probably suppresses the decomposition of (III), more of which isomerises into (IV). For example, under these conditions, benzyl phenyldithiocarbamate (5 g. in 40 ml acetone) and phenylamidine chloride (4 g. in 50 ml acetone), when mixed, afforded 5 g. of (IVa).

Bis-phenylamidine Sulphide Dihydrochloride (VIIa).—The product, m.p. 156°, is very unstable; its aqueous solutions are acidic and the liberated acid could be titrated with alkali; On keeping, it gradually decomposed and deposited 1-phenylthiocarbamide. (Found: C, 49.50; H, 4.68; N, 16.02; S, 9.32; equiv., 168.2. $C_{14}H_{14}N_4S$, 2HCl requires C, 48.98; H, 4.66; N, 16.32; S, 9.33%; equiv., 171.5). It afforded a picrate, m.p. 141°. On gently refluxing with ethanol it formed 1-phenylamidino-1-phenylthiocarbamide hydrochloride (m.p. 158°), identified by its oxidation to the related Hector's base¹¹. Treatment with ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide afforded a crystalline, sulphur free product which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 147°, and identified as *NN'*-diphenylguanidine through its undepressed mixed m.p. with an authentic sample. The ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide liquor on acidification precipitated 1-phenylthiocarbamide, m.p. 153°, and the filtrate showed a good positive test for thiocyanic acid when tested with ferric chloride.

The identity of this product as bis-phenylamidine sulphide dihydrochloride (VIIa) was established by its synthesis. Acetone solutions of 1-phenylthiocarbamide (6g. in 40 ml) and phenylamidine chloride (5 g. in 50 ml) were mixed and cooled to -5°. Almost immediately, a colorless, feathery light product separated, which on keeping afforded a microcrystalline powder, m.p. 156°. It could not be crystallised from any of the common solvents. It is extremely soluble in cold water and the aqueous solutions, which are strongly acidic, decompose on keeping. (Found: N, 16.70; equiv., 168.6. $C_{14}H_{14}N_4S$, 2HCl requires N, 16.32%; equiv., 171.5). The compound did not depress the m.p. of the product (VIIa). Their general chemical behaviour also was found identical.

S-Benzyl N-Phenylamidino phenyldithiocarbamate Hydrochloride (IVa): *The Water-insoluble Product*, m.p. 157°.—To remove the likely impurities of bis-phenylamidine sulphide dihydrochloride and 1-phenylthiocarbamide, formed by its decomposition, the product was washed with water, followed by acetone. It could not be crystallised but was purified by repeated precipitation with acetone from its methanolic solution; m.p. 158°. (Found: C, 60.12; H, 4.53; N, 10.16; Cl, 8.97; S, 15.70; equiv., 401.2. $C_{21}H_{19}N_3S_2$, HCl requires C, 60.94; H, 4.83; N, 10.15; Cl, 8.58%; S, 15.47; equiv., 413.5). It afforded a picrate, m.p. 129°. On basification, the free base obtained was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 145°. (Found: C, 67.11; H, 4.94; N, 11.55; S, 17.60. $C_{21}H_{19}N_3S_2$ requires C, 66.84; H, 5.03; N, 11.14; S, 16.97%). The base was found desulphurisable with warm alkali plumbite solution. On boiling with alkali, the smell of benzylmercaptan was apparent. Ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide decomposed it almost quantitatively into *NN'*-diphenylguanidine (about 1 g. from 2 g of IVa).

Expt. 2. Interaction of Benzyl *p*-Tolyldithiocarbamate with *p*-Tolylamidine Chloride

A chilled acetone solution of benzyl *p*-tolyldithiocarbamate (14 g.), prepared by benzylation of ammonium *p*-tolyldithiocarbamate^{13,14} with benzyl chloride in cold ethanolic medium (m.p. 89°) (Found: S, 22.94. $C_{13}H_{13}NS_2$ requires S, 23.47%), when mixed with *p*-tolylamidine chloride⁸ (6 g.) afforded a water-soluble dihydrochloride (3 g.), m.p. 161°.

followed by deposition of a water-insoluble product (6 g.), m.p. 181°, corresponding to (IVb) and (VIIb) respectively.

Bis-p-tolylamidino sulphide dihydrochloride (VIIb) is a colorless, crystalline powder, m.p. 151°. (Found: N, 14.64; equiv., 183.7. $C_{16}H_{18}N_4S$, 2HCl requires N, 15.09%; equiv., 185.5). It afforded a picrate, m.p. 154°.

The same product was obtained when 1-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide and *p*-tolylamidino chloride¹⁷ were allowed to react in an acetone medium; m.p. 154°. (Found: N, 14.72. $C_{16}H_{18}N_4S$, 2HCl requires N, 15.09%). It did not show any depression in m.p. when mixed with the product described above.

S-Benzyl N-p-tolylamidino-p-tolyldithiocarbamate hydrochloride (IVb) m.p. 181° was purified by precipitation with acetone from its methanolic solution, m.p. 181°. (Found: C, 62.22; H, 5.10; N, 9.52; S, 14.38; equiv., 438.2. $C_{23}H_{23}N_3S_2$, HCl requires C, 62.51; H, 5.43; N, 9.51; S, 14.49%; equiv., 441.5). It afforded a picrate, m.p. 135°, and on basification, a base was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 148°. (Found: N, 9.97; S, 15.62. $C_{23}H_{23}N_3S_2$ requires N, 10.37; S, 15.80%).

Expt. 3. Interaction of Benzyl p-Tolyldithiocarbamate with Phenylamidino Chloride

On reaction, as described above, benzyl *p*-tolyldithiocarbamate (14 g.) and phenylamidino chloride (10 g.) afforded a water-soluble product (3 g.), m.p. 150°, followed by a water-insoluble compound (6 g.), m.p. 164°, corresponding to (VIIa) and (IVe) respectively.

S-Benzyl N-phenylamidino-p-tolyldithiocarbamate hydrochloride (IVe) is a colorless, crystalline solid, m.p. 164°. (Found: N, 9.86; S, 14.50; equiv., 422.7. $C_{22}H_{21}N_3S_2$, HCl requires N, 9.82; S, 14.07%; equiv., 427.5). It afforded a picrate, m.p. 150°; the free base was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 140°. (Found: S, 16.71. $C_{22}H_{21}N_3S_2$ requires S, 16.36%).

Expt. 4. Interaction of Benzyl Phenylidithiocarbamate with p-Tolylamidino Chloride

Cold acetone solution of benzyl phenylidithiocarbamate (13 g.) and *p*-tolylamidino chloride (8 g.) on working up, as in other similar experiments, afforded a water-soluble dihydrochloride (4 g.), m.p. 151°, which was found identical with the dihydrochloride isolated in Expt. 2, and a water-insoluble product (7.5 g), m.p. 172°, corresponding to (VIIb) and (IVd) respectively.

S-Benzyl N-p-Tolylamidino phenylidithiocarbamate Hydrochloride (IVd).—The water-insoluble product is a colorless light solid. It was purified by reprecipitation with acetone from its methanolic solutions; m.p. 172°. (Found: C, 61.45; H, 4.66; N, 9.80; S, 14.32; equiv., 422.5. $C_{22}H_{21}N_3S_2$, HCl requires C, 61.75; H, 5.14; N, 9.82; S, 14.07%; equiv., 427.5). It afforded a picrate, m.p. 130°. The free base obtained on basification was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 141°. (Found: N, 10.41. $C_{22}H_{21}N_3S_2$ requires N, 10.74%).

Expt. 5. Interaction of Benzyl Phenylidithiocarbamate with p-Chlorophenylamidino Chloride

As in the above experiments, a chilled acetone solution of benzyl phenylidithiocarbamate (14 g.), when mixed with a cold acetone solution of *p*-chlorophenylamidino chloride¹⁷

and allowed to stand, a water-soluble dihydrochloride, m.p. 170°, first separated, followed by another water-insoluble product, m.p. 162°, corresponding to (VII, where Ar = *p*-chlorophenyl) and (IVe) respectively.

Bis-p-chlorophenylamidine sulphide dihydrochloride is a colorless, crystalline, water-soluble solid, m.p. 170°. (Found: N, 13.31. $C_{14}H_{16}N_4S_2Cl_4$, 2HCl requires N, 13.59%). This was found identical, through its undepressed mixed m.p. with the product obtained by the interaction of 1-*p*-chlorophenylthiocarbamide and *p*-chlorophenylamidine chloride in acetone, m.p. 170°. (Found: N, 13.49. $C_{14}H_{16}N_4Cl_2S$, HCl requires N, 13.59%).

S-Benzyl N-p-Chlorophenylamidinophenylidithiocarbamate Hydrochloride (IVe).—The product was purified by precipitation with acetone from its methanolic solution, m.p. 162° (Found: N, 9.80; S, 14.52; equiv., 443.3. $C_{21}H_{18}N_2ClS_2$, HCl requires N, 9.37; S, 14.28%; equiv., 448). On basification, free base obtained was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 150°. (Found: N, 10.17. $C_{21}H_{18}N_2S_2$ requires N, 10.19%).

Oxidative Debenzylation and Cyclisation of S-Benzyl N-Arylamidino-aryldithiocarbamates: Formation of 3-Arylimino-4-aryl-5-thio-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines

Expt. 6. 3-Phenylimino-4-phenyl-5-thio-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (Ia).—A typical set of details pertaining to the preparation of (Ia, where Ar=phenyl) are as follows: *S-Benzyl N-phenylamidino phenylidithiocarbamate* (IVa) hydrochloride (5 g.), made into paste with a little chloroform, was treated with bromine until the colour of bromine persisted. The reaction mixture warmed up considerably, evolving lachrymatory fumes of benzyl bromide. After keeping for 2 hr., the solid product (4 g.) was washed with ethanol, followed by ether. This was a hydrobromide, m.p. 151°. (Found: Equiv., 369.5. $C_{14}H_{11}N_3S_2$, HBr requires equiv., 366). On boiling with ethanol it was hydrolysed and afforded the related free base, m.p. 164°. (Found: C, 58.66; H, 3.77; N, 14.54; S, 23.30. $C_{14}H_{11}N_3S_2$ requires C, 58.94; H, 3.85; N, 14.73; S, 22.46%).

The compound was not desulphurisable with warm sodium plumbite solution. It was found unreactive towards phenyl isocyanate, phenyl isothiocyanate, carbon disulphide, nitrous acid, benzyl chloride, moderately strong acids, and alkalis. Treatment with warm ethanolic sodium sulphide solution, however, decomposed it and diphenylguanidine was isolated in considerable quantities from the decomposition products.

Expt. 7. 3-p-Tolylimino-4-p-tolyl-5-thio-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (Ib).—The *S*-benzyl *N-p*-tolylamidino-*p*-tolylidithiocarbamate hydrochloride (IVb) on reaction with bromine, under conditions outlined in the preceding experiment, afforded a hydrobromide, m.p. 154°. (Found: Equiv., 389. $C_{16}H_{13}N_3S_2$, HBr requires equiv., 394). On basification, it afforded the related free base, crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 149°. (Found: C, 61.20; H, 4.69; N, 13.22; S, 19.87. $C_{16}H_{13}N_3S_2$ requires C, 61.34; H, 4.78; N, 13.41; S, 20.44%).

Expt. 8. 3-Phenylimino-4-p-tolyl-5-thio-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (Ic).—On reaction with bromine, the *S*-benzyl-*N*-phenylamidino-*p*-tolylidithiocarbamate hydrochloride (IVc) afforded a hydrobromide, m.p. 158°. (Found: Equiv., 375.2. $C_{15}H_{13}N_3S_2$, HBr requires equiv., 380). On basification, the free base obtained was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 146°. (Found: C, 59.65; H, 4.52; N, 14.34; S, 20.05. $C_{15}H_{13}N_3S_2$ requires C, 60.20; H, 4.34; N, 14.05; S, 21.40%).

Expt. 9. 3-p-Tolylimino-4-phenyl-5-thio-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (Id).—S-Benzyl N-p-tolylamidino phenyldithiocarbamate hydrochloride (IVd) on oxidation with bromine, as above, afforded a hydrobromide, m.p. 148°. (Found: Equiv., 376.2. $C_{15}H_{13}N_3S_2$, HBr requires 380). This free base was crystallised from ethanol in fine needles, m.p. 146°. (Found: C, 59.73; H, 4.47; N, 14.22; S, 20.88. $C_{15}H_{13}N_3S_2$ requires C, 60.20; H, 4.34; N, 14.05; S, 21.40%).

Expt. 10. 3-p-Chlorophenylimino-4-phenyl-5-thio-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (Ie).—The S-benzyl N-p-chlorophenylamidino phenyldithiocarbamate (IVe) hydrochloride, on oxidation with bromine as above, afforded a hydrobromide, m.p. 178°. (Found: Equiv., 396.7. $C_{14}H_{10}N_3ClS_2$, HBr requires equiv., 400.5). It afforded a free base, crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 165°. (Found: C, 53.10; H, 3.30; N, 12.83; S, 19.75. $C_{14}H_{10}N_3ClS_2$ requires C, 52.58; H, 3.12; N, 13.14; S, 20.03%).

The following main IR absorption characteristics were noted in the IR spectrum (chloroform) in the product (Ia, where $Ar = Ar' = Ph$): 3430s, 3020s, 1664m, 1504w, 1508w, 1490m, 1440s, 1332s, 1298s, 1252s, 1196w, 1102m, 1068s, 1035s, 880m, 860w, 870w cm^{-1} .

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